

A STUDY OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS ATTITUDE TOWARDS ADJUSTMENT

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Abstract:

The concept of attitude and adjustment was originally a biological one and was concerned with adaptation to physical environment for survival. Objectives: To find out the significance difference of attitude and adjustment in higher secondary students in terms of the variables. Population: The investigator adopted the survey method in the present study selecting the higher secondary students of Vellore District. 300 samples were collected from Government, Aided and private schools. Attitude Scale by N. S. Chauhan and Saroj Aurora, Meerut and Adjustment scale by A. K. P. Sinha and R. P. Singh. The Reliability for attitude Inventory is 0.79. & Adjustment scale was 0.64. Major Findings: The higher secondary students did not significantly differ in their adjustment and attitude towards gender, locality of school, type of management, religion and parental occupation.

Attitude:

"Attitude" is a familiar word and is used freely to express one's way of thinking, feeling or behaving. The term "Attitude" has been used by psychologists in several connotations and there are a number of agreed definitions of the term. Allport (1929) defined it's mental or neural state of readiness, organized through experiences exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual response to all the objects and situations with which it is related. According to Thomas and Zmiecki (1981) by attitude we understand a process of individual consciousness which determines real or possible activity of the individual counterpart of the social value, activity in whatever form in the bond between them.

The definition stresses that attitude is a generalized pattern of perception of action which is a result of integration of various experiences. In the Lund berg (1929) "an attitude denotes the general set of the organism as a whole toward an object of situation which calls for adjustment. Kohler (1929) remarked "an attitude involves on the sensory field by processes originating in other parts of the nervous system". According to Bogardus (1931) "attitude is a tendency to act toward or against something in the environment which becomes there by positive or a negative value". Morgan (1936) "attitude is literally mental postures, guides for conduct which each new experience is referred before a response is made. According to Warren (1934) in the dictionary of psychology, attitude is defined as the specific mental disposition in coming experience where by the experience is modified or a condition of readiness for certain type of activities. Guilford (1954) defined attitude as a personal disposition common to individuals but to react to object, situation or positions in ways that can be called favorable or unfavorable. According to Freeman (1968) an attitude is a dispositional readiness to respond to certain situations, persons or objects in a constant manner which has been learned and has become one typical mode of response. Though attitude and opinion are allied terms they are synonyms. Attitude denotes the inner feelings or belief of a person towards a psychological phenomenon. Opinion is therefore a verbal expression of attitude.

Adjustment:

We think of adjustment as psychological survival in the same way as biologist uses the term adaptation to describe physiological survival. Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its need and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. The term 'adjustment' broadly refers to manage environmental and internal demands and conflicts among demands. The term 'adjustment' used interchangeably with the concepts such as mastery, defence, coping and adaptation. A working definition refers that it has any response to external life strains that serves to prevent, avoid and control external distress. Several investigators attempted to classify the adjustment styles of individuals to environmental situations, but no single and unanimously accepted method has yet emerged.

Adjustment according to modern concept is both a process and a state. As a process, it is continuous and complex. It depends upon the entire organization of psycho-physical systems within the individual and the relation of this organization to the environment. As a state it is the condition of harmony arrived at by a person whom we may call adjusted. Proper adjustment is necessary for leading happy life. Vasishtha (1989) reveals that well adjusted students demonstrate a realistic self concept and high academic achievement while maladjusted ones may back in both the self concept and academic achievement. Adjustment is a harmonious relationship with the environment in which most individual needs are satisfied in socially acceptable ways, and resulting in forms of behavior which may range from passive conformity to vigorous action. According to Singh (1983) adjustment is a precarious and ever-changing balance between the needs and desires of the individuals on the

one hand and the demands of the environments or society on the other. Adjustment is process by which a twinge organism maintains a balance between needs and circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs.

Significance of the Study:

Education has remained an instrument of change and national development of any country. It is a social process and the medium for the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills, attitudes and adjustment for survival in a changing world. The strengthening of democratic institutions witnessed the world over including India and the rapid increase in globalization has become more prominent in the 21st century. Nations desire closer cooperation, improvement in the quality of life, respect for the rule of law and Human Rights and peaceful co-existence among communities and nations constitute global issues of concern.

The Method adopted to collect the information /data was the normative survey. The study is descriptive in nature and residing under the head of Descriptive Research. The related data was collected with the help of a custom made Questionnaire, higher secondary students in Vellore District.

Sample:

The sample of the study consists of 300 higher secondary students from Tamilnadu in Vellore District. Simple Random Sampling method was adopted.

Statistical Treatment:

The collected data was analyzed statistically by using The Arithmetic Mean (x), The Standard deviation (σ) and The 't' test (t). F test.

Objectives of the Study:

To find out whether there is any significant difference in the attitude and adjustment of higher secondary students owing to differences in terms of the variables

- ✓ Gender : Male/ Female
- ✓ Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Type of Management : Government / Aided/ Private
- ✓ Religion : Hindu / Muslim / Christian
- ✓ Parental Occupation : Govt employed / Self employed

Hypotheses:

There is no significant difference in the attitude and adjustment of higher secondary students owing to differences in terms of the variables

- ✓ Gender : Male/ Female
- ✓ Locality of School : Rural / Urban
- ✓ Type of Management : Government / Aided/ Private
- ✓ Religion : Hindu / Muslim / Christian
- ✓ Parental Occupation : Govt employed / Self employed

Tools Used for the Study:

- ✓ Attitude Scale by N. S. Chauhan and Saroj Aurora, Meerut. To be used by the tester afterwards. The tester is to fill the schedule of the sheet himself. He must tick himself the item ticked by the testee and fill up. Attitude wise total score of the ticked items be filled in the table space, provided on the facing page of the scoring sheet.
- ✓ Adjustment scale by A. K. P. Sinha and R. P. Singh, This tool consists of as many as 60 statements and each statement has two responses i.e. 'Yes' or 'No'. The maximum score for this scale is 60 and 0 is the minimum score. There is no time limit to complete the research tool but most of the individuals complete within 45 minutes.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Gender and Attitude:

Table 1: 't' – Values between Gender of Higher Secondary with Respect in their Attitude

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	139	132.74	14.54	1.06	NS
Female	121	134.61	13.67		

It is evident from Table 1, the calculated 't' value is 1.06, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.

Locality of school and Attitude:

Table 2: 't' – Values between Locality of School of Higher Secondary Students With Respect in their Attitude

Locality of school	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	134	134.41	14.44	0.938	NS
Urban	126	132.76	13.83		

It is evident from Table 2, the calculated 't' value is 0.938, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.

Type of Management and Attitude:

Table 3: 'F' Values for Attitude Scores–Higher Secondary Students – Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	416.970	208.485	5	1.042	NS
Within Groups	51432.334	200.126	257		
Total	51849.304		259		

Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 1.042, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.

Religion and Attitude:

Table 4: 'F' Values for Attitude Scores–Higher Secondary Students – Based On Religion

Religion	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	108.761	54.380	2	0.270	NS
Within Groups	51740.543	201.325	257		
Total	51849.304		259		

Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 0.270, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.

Parental Occupation and Attitude:

Table 5: 't' – Values between Parental Occupation of Higher Secondary Students with Respect in their Attitude

Parental Occupation	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Government employ	122	133.12	14.21	0.531	NS
Self-employ	138	134.05	14.12		

It is evident from Table 5; the calculated 't' value is 0.531, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between government employ and self-employ of higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.

Gender and Adjustment:

Table 6: 't' – Values between Gender of Higher Secondary with Respect in their Adjustment

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Male	139	50.50	4.41	0.074	NS
Female	121	50.54	4.71		

It is evident from Table 6, the calculated 't' value is 0.074, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Locality of School and Adjustment:

Table 7: 't' – Values between Locality of School of Higher Secondary With Respect in their Adjustment

Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Level of Significance
Rural	134	50.61	4.69	0.351	NS
Urban	126	50.42	4.41		

It is evident from Table 7, the calculated 't' value is 0.351, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Type of Management and Adjustment:

Table 8: 'F' Values for Adjustment Scores–Higher Secondary Students – Based on Type of Management

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	25.446	12.723	5	0.613	NS
Within Groups	5337.416	20.768	257		
Total	5362.862		259		

Table 8, the calculated 'F' value is 0.613, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their adjustment of higher secondary students.

Religion and Adjustment:

Table 9: ‘F’ Values for Adjustment Scores–Higher Secondary Students – Based on Religion

Religion	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	‘F’ Value	Level of Significance
Between Groups	42.346	21.173	2	1.023	NS
Within Groups	5320.515	20.702	257		
Total	5362.862		259		

Table 9, the calculated ‘F’ value is 1.023, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their adjustment of higher secondary students.

Parental Occupation and Adjustment:

Table 10: ‘t’ – Values between Parental Occupation of Higher Secondary With Respect in their Adjustment

Parental Occupation	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ Value	Level of Significance
Government Employ	122	51.09	4.35	1.89	NS
Self-Employ	138	50.02	4.67		

It is evident from Table 10, the calculated ‘t’ value is 1.89, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is a no significant difference found between government employ and self-employ of higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their attitude of higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between government employ and self-employ of higher secondary students with respect to their attitude.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between male and female higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between rural and urban higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their adjustment of higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among sub samples of religion with respect to their adjustment of higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference found between government employ and self-employ of higher secondary students with respect to their adjustment.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The study may be extended to higher level of education such as to colleges, universities etc.
- ✓ A study may be undertaken to know the home adjustment and scientific attitude of high school students.
- ✓ The study may be extended to a large sample and to other districts of Tamilnadu.

Conclusion:

In fact, it can be said that the whole human capital formation of the country is dependent on attitude in an urgent need for the development of proper adjustment among the students. Basically, attitude of students refers to wishes, feeling, ideas, liking or disliking towards adjustment. Thus this study recommends, every students has to check attitude of during admission or before entering into course through entrance examination. It helps to identify the students’ level of attitude towards profession and give more training to students to develop the attitude towards adjustment.

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